
Role Of Intellectual Property Rights For SMEs

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Abstract:

Globalization has enhanced competitiveness in the international market and has deep influence on the way enterprises work. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are too becoming increasingly involved in the market basically as part of supply chains and also due to expansion and growth. But, they face the problem of responding to the new economic world order because they are not familiar with the best ways to manage their knowledge assets. They face different types of Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) challenges and do need to evolve strategies suiting different conditions to exist in competitive market. In this context, it is important to re-look at the basic issues relating to need for protecting intellectual wealth, policy measures and steps taken for creating IPR culture in SMEs. The paper argues that the ability to create, access and use knowledge is the fundamental determinant of global competitiveness of enterprises and economies which highlights the importance of IPRs. The paper examines all these issues in the context of Indian Small and Medium Enterprises.

Keywords: *Globalization, International Market, Small and Medium Enterprises, Innovation and Intellectual Property Rights.*

Introduction:

SMEs face a major challenge in the new environment because they are not familiar with the best ways to manage their knowledge assets. They face different types of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) challenges and do need to evolve strategies suiting different conditions to exist in competitive market. In this context, it is equally important to re-look at the basic issues relating to, reasons for economy environment change, need for protecting intellectual wealth, policy measures and steps taken for 4 creating IPR culture in SMEs. The ability to create, access and use knowledge is the 5 fundamental determinant of global competitiveness of enterprises and economies which highlight the importance of IPRs. The paper examines all these issues in the context of Indian SMEs.

The traditional factors/determinants of wealth creation (Land, Labour and Capital) 1 does not occupy the central position in today's market economy. It is the manner one manages Knowledge that decides the competitive edge. SMEs are becoming increasingly involved in global competitive markets, basically as part of supply 2 chains and also due to expansion and growth. SMEs have traditionally relied more on local markets and are currently less equipped to face market challenges of a highly competitive environment. In addition to local government help, SMEs in these regions need to re-examine and modify their competitive strategies by fully 3 incorporating innovation within their people, processes and products.

Indian Small and Medium Industries in the Era of Globalization:

Worldwide, SMEs account for approximately 95% of the business population. Given the significant role of SMEs in the national economy in terms of their sizeable contribution to GDP, employment generation, export performance, and achieving sustainable national economic development, most governments have placed increasing emphasis on facilitating the creation and development of the national SMEs sector. In the context of increasing international trade, specialization seems to be a better mode to achieve prosperity rather than diversity in activities of an enterprise. The majority of the world's large companies provide multiple services but purchase many components and goods from smaller companies that are engaged in one activity. Thus, SMEs can prove to be an effective player for economic growth through their participation in global trade. SMEs also drive economic development by creating a valuable source of employment.

A typical SME can be defined as an enterprise in market economies founded on the basis of innovation and with the help of entrepreneurial spirit, usually governed by 7 owners or partial owners in a personalized way. A classification of SMEs is determined by the criteria that vary across countries. Some adopt registered capital, capital expenditures or turnover as a standard. In accordance with the provision of the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Development Act, 2006 of India, the small and medium enterprises are classified into two classes.

1. **Manufacturing Enterprises:** The Enterprises engaged in the manufacturing or production of goods pertaining to any industry specified in the first schedule to the Industries (Development and Regulation) Act, 1951. The manufacturing enterprises are

defined in the terms of investment in plant and machinery. For Small enterprise, the investment in plant and machinery has to be more than twenty five lakh rupees but should not exceed five crore rupees; and for Medium enterprise, the investment in plant and machinery has to be more than five crore rupees but it should not exceed ten crore rupees.

2. **Service Enterprises:** The enterprises engaged in providing or rendering of services and are defined in the terms of investment in equipment. If investment in equipment is more than ten lakh rupees but does not exceed two crore rupees, it is a small enterprise; and if investment in equipment is more than two crore rupees but does not exceed five crore rupees, it is medium enterprise.

Intellectual Property: Meaning and Kinds:

The term 'intellectual property' has been used for almost one hundred and fifty years to refer general area of law that encompasses copyright, patents, designs and 34 trademarks, as well as a host of related rights. IP laws regulate creation, use and exploitation of intellectual creations which are sine qua non for the economic and technological development of a nation and the prosperity achieved by any nation is the result of exploitation of their intellectual property. In this era of globalization, especially after the establishment of WTO, intellectual property laws have assumed great importance. The system of intellectual property rights creates property rights over knowledge. IP rights may be defined as exclusive rights granted by the State giving the owner the right to exclude others from the commercial exploitation of a given invention, new/original design, trademark, literary and artistic work and/or new variety of plant. By providing a fair degree of

exclusivity over the exploitation of innovation(s), the system of IP rights creates an incentive to invest in scientific, technological, and organizational R&D activities so as to reduce the risk of free-riding by others while commercially exploiting product and process innovations. India is a fast developing economy and there is growing concern as to how the stronger IP protection, demanded by the TRIPs Agreement, is going to affect such an economy. After India became party to the TRIPs agreement all the existing intellectual property laws in India were subjected to considerable changes. New laws were also introduced to satisfy her obligations under the TRIPs. There is considerable increase in the litigation in India in the last decade. Various kinds of IP performing different functions have been incorporated in municipal laws. While a patent is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which is a product or a process that provides a new way of doing something, or offers a new technical solution to a problem, a trademark or brand-name is a distinctive sign which identifies certain goods or services as those produced or provided by a specific person or enterprise. An industrial design or simply design is the ornamental or aesthetic aspect of an article produced by industry or handicraft; registration. Copyright is a legal term describing rights given to creators for their literary and artistic works (including computer software). Related rights are granted to performing artists; producers of sound recordings and broadcasting organizations in their radio and television programme. A geographical indication, a form of community IP, is a sign used on goods that have a specific geographical origin and often possess qualities or a reputation that are due to that place of origin. Another form of IP which is not generally known among or readily accessible to persons that normally deal with the kind of information in question is known

as Trade Secrets or Undisclosed Information. It has commercial value because it is secret, and has been subject to reasonable steps to keep it secret by the person lawfully in control of the 37 information. It is important to note that enterprises attach more importance to patent and trademark in the context of economic growth. The growing importance of patent in particular is visible from the increasing applications filed by firms in foreign countries. The reasons for the above according to Esteban Burr-one include - the shift towards knowledge-based industries making intangible assets as the source of competitive advantage for firms, the outsourcing of manufacturing activities to subcontractors, legislative changes at the national, regional and international levels, the expansion of palatable subject matter, and a surge in patenting among 38 universities and public-sector R&D institutions.

Planning New Initiatives for SMEs:

The biggest challenge is enhancing IPR awareness. The Ministry of Small-Scale Industries has taken steps to create awareness about IPR. It is important to note that a plan for promoting the IP culture keeping in view the existing bottlenecks needs to be evolved. Looking at the nature of the SMEs and their financial capabilities it is imperative for the government to intervene into the matter and take actions for facilitating more IP registrations. Protecting inventions in foreign countries could be very expensive which most SSIs would not be in a position to afford. It will be wise to exempt R&D type SMEs from paying the official fee for patenting and maintaining patents. Most of the SMEs in India do not have the financial stability to take the innovation to the final stage and many a times the invention falls short on account of inventive step and thus not granted patent, in this context sound arguments in favour of

allowing registration for utility models need to be advanced. Further, it is also important to note that managing Knowledge requires proper understanding of the value of IP which in turn largely depends on the process of IP auditing. Thus a brief examination of Utility Model Protection, IP valuation and IP audit in the context of SMEs is not out of place. a) Utility Model: As the international documents on IP are silent on the meaning of utility model, a survey of national laws suggest that Utility models are a form of patent-like protection for minor or incremental innovations. They tend to protect the functional aspect of a product. One of the main rationales behind this second-tier patent systems is that such systems improve access to patent protection for individuals and SMEs. In addition, the quick grant of a second-tier patent is thought to make such protection suitable for products with a short life-cycle. It is often claimed that utility model systems are particularly advantageous for SMEs, especially in developing countries. It is quite likely that SMEs have a large presence in those industries where cumulative innovation is the norm and copying is rife. Indeed, it is also often argued that a cheap and rapid second tier patent regime would improve the legal environment for SMEs, especially those which are engaged in an ongoing process of innovation and adaptation. This is more so in relation to certain product sectors which are concerned, not so much with revolutionary technological breakthroughs, but more so with incremental or improvement innovation. For another, it may even be that more innovations, both of the breakthrough and incremental varieties, emanate from SMEs than from larger multinational conglomerates. If this is so, it is important to gauge whether the current patent regime is attuned to the needs of SMEs and the types of inventions they produce. Another reason why utility models may be good for SMEs is

that the cost factor may inhibit them from using the patent system as much as they would desire.

IP Valuation:

While big enterprises have become leaders by the effective creation, extraction and leveraging of their IP through efficient IP management, the SMEs have been slow in realizing the potential of IP management in increasing their competitiveness. The primary reason for valuing IP is to maximize its value and therefore the value of the owner organization through optimum management decisions. There are various scenarios where valuation is required and needed, some examples are: i) An accurate IP valuation is required for buying or selling a company, establishing joint ventures, and executing mergers and acquisitions. ii) When negotiating a license contract, both parties must be clear about the values involved. iii) To finance their development plans, many knowledge intensive companies can only offer their own IP as collateral. Due to insufficient knowledge about IP and valuation, banks are as yet reluctant to accept such assets. iv) Knowing the value of their IP is important for possible tax deductions and tax compliance. Accounting standards are generally not helpful in representing IP in company accounts and as a result these are often under-valued and mismanaged. v) Accurate IP appraisal is required in the event of IP rights infringement or breach of contract. vi) Research, development, legal, industrial protection application and commercialization decisions involve high but measurable levels of risk. IP valuation facilitates cost effective decision-making and helps to understand and deal with the risks involved. It is important to note that in view of the managerial and resource constraints typically confronting SMEs, it seems unlikely that the negative cost-benefit conclusions arrived at by most large firms in

regard to greater disclosure of intangibles will be any less stark. Managerial and other limitations within SMEs make the measurement, management and development of knowledge and other intangible assets difficult and costly to achieve because of the absence of the necessary formalized systems of feedback, reporting and the detailed statistical information and monitoring systems necessary to underpin these practices. The high set-up costs associated with developing the above managerial infrastructure tends, therefore to result in most SMEs concluding that such intangible management systems will "not find a suitable home in a SME environment, and will typically be 64 deemed 'unworkable' by SME management" . The observation justifies the state intervention at two levels, first, spreading awareness about the utility of valuation and thus efficient management of IP assets and second, making assistance available for the SMEs so that the cost involved in the process may be minimal. It is further substantiated by the observation of Robert Watson that 'the valuation and reporting of SME intangible assets is likely to produce few benefits whilst potentially being very costly in terms of its usage of scarce resources, namely the owner-manager's time and energy and the financial costs of engaging outside professionals.

IP Audit:

In an enterprise setup, a large number of intellectual assets may be involved. In such a situation, how can the company's officers be confident that they are aware of all of the company's intellectual property assets? One solution is to 67 perform an intellectual property audit. The intellectual property audit is a management tool for the assessment of the value and risk of intellectual property assets. The IP audit, once completed, should provide a significant volume of data and analysis that addresses how well an enterprise is equipped to

participate in economic growth based on intellectual property assets. It should give an objective, comprehensive picture of existing strategies, infrastructure, capacity, need, institutions, competitive advantages and challenges. Such data and analysis are a precondition for defining realistically attainable economic and 68 development objectives. Thus an IP audit is an inspection of the intellectual property owned, used, or acquired by a business as well as a review of its management, maintenance, exploitation, and enforcement. It is believed that the focus on short-term results causes intellectual property, and related corporate 69 performance, to remain somewhat behind. The purpose of the intellectual property audit should be financial, technical and legal. 70 Any aspect if left would not suffice the audit exercise. It has to include an evaluation of the procedure in place at the company for maintaining the company's IP assets, avoiding unauthorized use of the intellectual property rights of others and 71 valuation of intellectual assets. It is a continuous exercise as the value of intellectual property asset is generally not stagnant. There are many stages of the life of an intellectual property asset and at each of such stages; the value of the 72 concerned asset may differ. Just as companies develop varying personalities in their corporate culture, such as brand awareness, competitiveness, and innovativeness, they should similarly strive to make IP awareness a trait that spans all parts of their business all of the time.

Conclusion:

The foregoing discussion suggests that intellectual property has business implications at various points across the enterprise, and each of these points has a role to play in its management. An effective IP management scheme for SME includes appreciation of the fact that the value and role of intellectual asset keeps changing with

time. Thus, it must adapt to business objectives and changes in technology. IP audit is therefore the starting point. After having realized the importance of IP for SMEs in India, it is now imperative for the government to work in the direction of promoting competitiveness of SMEs and thus making them equipped to manage their knowledge resources. The present paper

presented arguments for evolving a plan for aspects like utility model protection, IP valuation and IP audit for SMEs in the special context of India. The paper thus takes us to the conclusion that growth depends on managing knowledge which in turn depends on acquiring knowledge about the amount and kind of knowledge possessed by an enterprise.